

A Review on Lead Free Piezoelectric Perovskites and their Composites

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Abstract

This study is on brief description of polymer-perovskite ceramic composites and reviews of lead-free composites with special focus on sodium potassium niobate, barium titanate and sodium niobate material systems. Composites are a better choice for various applications like energy storage devices, sensors etc. rather than pure polymers. Modification of composites can improve the electrical properties of the composites. The aim of studying about composites is to link scientific studies and technical applications of polymer composites.

Keywords: Polymers, composites, ceramics, perovskites

Introduction

For centuries, organic and inorganic materials like ceramics, polymer, etc., have been playing a significant role in meeting the emerging human needs. Smart and functional materials are of great interest in present community, based on its applications. The ceramics and polymers have been used as the basic materials in the field of material science and their co-existence has led to the discovery of new classes of functional materials, i.e. composites. Some electronic materials need combination of desirable properties which cannot be obtained from single phase materials. The material imposed limitations can be overcome by combining two or more classes of materials in a single material [1]. A composite material has been defined as tailored material system which consists two or more physically and chemically distinct phases with an interface separating them. The individual components of the composites are termed as constituent materials or phases. There are two categories of phases present in the composites, one is matrix phase and the other one is reinforcement phase. The matrix phase is a continuous phase which surrounds and supports the reinforcement phase by maintaining their relative positions. The reinforcement phase is embedded by the matrix phase and the reinforcement phase provides mechanical and physical properties to the matrix phase. The region where the matrix phase and reinforcement phases interact is known as interface. In most of the composite materials, this region has finite thickness because of chemical reactions between the filler and the matrix. In the composites, one of the phase will be responsible for providing one set of desirable properties and the other phase for providing another set of properties. The combination of two materials with different properties in a new composite structure, could lead to a material with superior performance.

Discussion

Perovskites: Perovskites are widely used as lead free piezoelectrics which serve as a better substitute for PZT (Lead zirconate titanate) compounds. A perovskite is any material with same type of crystal structure as calcium titanate. These crystallites exhibit simple cubic symmetry above a temperature known as the Curie point T_c . The simplest structure of a perovskite is cubic of ABO_3 type, where 'A' and 'B' are two cations of different sizes. Cations are larger than B and O is an anion that bonds the cations. This structure with A site cations located at the centre of oxygen where the positive and negative charge sites coincide without a dipole is termed as centrosymmetric with zero polarization. Below the Curie temperature, the cubic structure distorts and these crystallites take a tetragonal symmetry in which the cations are shifted from the centre. This creates a positive and negative charge sites resulting in the formation of an electric dipoles that can be shifted to certain allowed directions by the application of an electric field. The resulting electric dipole is responsible for the ferroelectric property. The most common variants are non cubic, orthorhombic and tetragonal phases.

Figure 1: The perovskite structure of PZT with a cubic lattice (Centrosymmetric with zero polarization)

The structure has noncentro symmetry with a net polarization as shown in figure 1. These materials can be made piezoelectric by poling. Electric dipoles represent a vector and dipole density is a vector field. Nearby dipoles tends to be aligned in regions called Weiss domains. The regions of the material with the same polarization orientation are referred as ferroelectric domains. When the sample is under strain-free conditions, all the domain states have the same energy, but when the electric field is applied, the free energy of the system becomes less by orienting the polarization along the field. As a result, poly crystals oriented randomly can be electrically poled to produce net piezoelectric coefficients. The poling shifts the dipole vector of each domain to the crystallographic direction which is nearest to the direction of the applied field. A stress applied on the material results in the separation of charges leading to a net polarization.

Variety of cations can fit together to form a perovskite structure and this can be empirically predicted by the following relationship:

$$t = \frac{R_A + R_O}{\sqrt{2}(R_B + R_O)}$$

where t is called tolerance factor, R_A , R_B and R_O are the ionic radii of the A, B cations and oxygen respectively. In a perovskite structure, if the bonding between all the ions is ionic, then the tolerance factor is 1.0 for a perfect perovskite structure. The structure of a perovskite material is cubic, when $0.95 < t < 1.0$. The structures with $t < 0.95$ tends to be slightly distorted but non-ferroelectric, and those with t slightly greater than 1 are ferroelectric.

Figure 2: The perovskite structure of PZT with a tetragonal lattice (Non-centrosymmetric with a net polarization).

Role of Defects in Perovskites: Perfect crystals with all sites occupied by identical atoms or ions at temperatures above 0 K do not exist [3]. Real materials always contain defects and its concentration increases with temperature. Structural imperfections such as point defects or vacancies, dislocations, grain boundaries can occur in ceramic materials. Intrinsic point defects are electrons and holes, interstitials, vacancies and substitution of

A-atom on the B-site [1, 2]. These defects occur mainly due to addition of impurity. Doping creates extrinsic point defects. Interfaces or grain boundaries can also be considered as defects and has a significant impact on the properties of the materials. In perovskites, the electrons, holes and oxygen vacancies are the possible charge carriers and the most mobile ionic species in perovskite oxides are oxygen vacancies [4, 9]. Depending on the ratio of the cations present, the perovskite oxide can be metal deficient or metal sufficient. A metal deficiency results in cation vacancies, whereas excess metal results in interstitial cations. The nature of disorder within the lattice controls the electronic and ionic properties of perovskites. The impurity cations occupies a site according to their charge and ionic radii. Large cations replace larger ions and vice versa.

Piezoelectric Composites and Its Connectivity: The demand for piezoelectric composites is growing and developing such materials with tailor made properties for particular applications is a necessity for the emerging needs of modern era. The arrangement of the constituent phases in a composite requires the introduction of the concept of connectivity developed by Newnham et al. in the late 1970s [10]. 10 connectivity patterns are shown in figure 3 which includes 0-0, 0-1, 0-2, 0-3, 1-1, 1-2, 2-2, 1-3, 2-3 and 3-3 where 0-3 and 1-3 has gained more prominence.

In this connectivity pattern, the first number indicate the physical connectivity of the active phase (ceramic) and second number the passive phase (polymer). Most simple one is 0-3 connectivity in which the ceramic fillers are incorporated in polymer matrix. The polymer composite with 0-3 connectivity has several advantages compared to other types because of their ease for production, their ability to tailor the properties by varying the weight ratio of the ceramic fillers. The reason for the relatively low piezoelectric properties of 0-3 type composite compared to 1-3 connectivity is due to the random distribution of ceramic particles in the polymer matrix and the declining effect of the non-conductive polymer matrix separating the piezo active particles [11].

Figure 3: Connectivity patterns for two-phase piezocomposites (after Newnham et al. 1978)

Advantages & Disadvantages of Ferroelectric Ceramics: Ferroelectric ceramics possess higher dielectric constant compared to ordinary insulating substances, making them useful for capacitor and energy storage applications. Ferroelectric ceramics also possess high electrochemical coupling and piezoelectric coefficients. This makes ferroelectric ceramics suitable candidate for high dielectric constant capacitors, piezoelectric transducers, and medical ultrasonic applications, etc. Despite of many advantages, ferroelectric ceramics has some disadvantages. High ϵ_r is obtained near T_c in ferroelectric ceramics. So, to exploit the high capacitance of these materials, the working temperature should be near T_c . But at T_c , there is a huge variation in the material's dielectric properties, which makes them disadvantageous for capacitor applications for a wide temperature range. The ferroelectric ceramics exhibit low dielectric strength and lack flexibility/elasticity and tend to be brittle due to its mechanical rigidity. They need high processing temperatures and possess high value of acoustic impedance which does not match with water or human body tissue. Also, polycrystalline ferroelectrics lose piezoelectricity at high temperatures. These disadvantages are against various device applications.

Non-Ferroelectric Polymers: Non-ferroelectric polymers are the subclass of polymers which are amorphous in nature which mainly include thermosets. These polymers are more stable than ferroelectric polymers. They have a good combination of mechanical properties, corrosion resistance, good thermal stability, electrical properties and excellent adhesion properties. These polymers are inexpensive than the ferroelectric polymers. The most commercially active examples of non-ferroelectric polymers include epoxy and phenolic thermosetting polymers.

Epoxy is a class of polymers which are mainly used as structural components and adhesives. Epoxy is composed of a two-component system, a liquid resin and a hardener or a cross-linker. On mixing, the hardener reacts with epoxides in the resin to create a densely linked network. Epoxy is a thermoset polymer, which cures into stronger form by supplying energy. In contrast to thermoplastics, thermosets cannot be melted or significantly softened by heating and are much stronger. Other example of non-ferroelectric polymer is polyvinyl alcohol.

Developments In Polymer Matrix Composites: Before 1940, the known ferroelectrics were Rochelle salt and potassium dihydrogen phosphate only. The birth of other ferroelectric ceramics took place in 1940's with the discovery of ferroelectricity in polycrystalline barium titanate [12]. The advantage of polycrystalline ceramics over single crystals is that polycrystalline ceramics can be dragged into any desired shape. The synthesizing technique of polycrystalline ceramics is cheaper than that of single crystal growth [13]. Therefore, the growth in the development of new ferroelectric ceramics played a vital role in the field of technology and industries. The BT ceramics were widely used in developing high dielectric constant capacitors, piezoelectric transducers, etc., Piezoelectrics are widely used because of its high electromechanical coupling factors and relatively good operation temperature range.

To get a ferroelectric that has superior piezoelectric performance, different perovskite piezoelectrics can be mixed to produce a single perovskite. The lead zirconate titanate PZT, a combination of lead zirconate and lead titanate, both of which are perovskite is the most popular perovskites till date. By 1950's, more research was done on development of many lead based ferroelectric ceramics such as lead titanate (PbTiO₃/PT), lead zirconate titanate (PZT), lead lanthanum zirconate titanate (PLZT) and relaxor ferroelectrics like lead magnesium niobate (PMN), etc. [14].

The lead based piezoelectric systems shows an excellent dielectric and piezoelectric properties near morphotropic phase boundary (MPB) which make it useful in piezoelectric applications [4]. But these lead based ferroelectric materials contain more than 60 weight percent of lead oxide, which can be a cause for various environmental problems [15-17]. Awareness about environmental issues has led WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment) and RoHS (Restriction of Hazardous Substances) to put a ban on the use of lead based materials [18] and these problems made research orient towards lead free systems [19-24]. The materials with high permittivity are required for capacitor applications and ferroelectric materials possess high value of permittivity near curie temperature.

For memory and piezoelectric applications, a stable P_{sat} or P_s is required and this can be achieved when the operating temperature is far below curie temperature [25]. The most popular piezoelectric materials are lead-based and PZT is one of them. PZT exhibits strong piezoelectric effects in the composition near morphotropic phase boundary [Pb(Zr_{0.52}Ti_{0.48})O₃]. The morphotropic phase boundary of PZT is almost vertical and maintains the excellent piezoelectric properties across a wide temperature range in the phase diagram.

Figure 4: Phase transition of PZT

The phase transition diagram in figure 4 shows a combination solution of ferroelectric PbTiO_3 with $T_C = 495^\circ\text{C}$, having tetragonal phase at room temperature, with antiferroelectric PbZrO_3 which is orthorhombic and has $T_C = 234^\circ\text{C}$ [3]. The morphotropic phase boundary (MPB) determines the piezo and dielectric properties of the material. For PZT, it indicates a state of structural change from rhombohedral to tetragonal where the two structures coexist. The doping of PZT can increase its properties.

Besides PZT, some newer generations that exhibit excellent piezoelectric properties were PbTiO_3 (PT) combined lead-based ferroelectrics such as $\text{Pb}(\text{Zn}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ (PZN) and $\text{Pb}(\text{Mg}_{1/3}\text{Nb}_{2/3})\text{O}_3$ (PMN). The piezoelectric charge coefficient of PZN-PT single crystal with the near-MPB composition (10% PT) was 2500 pC/N [26] and that of PMN-PT was 1500 pC/N [27]. In terms of electrical properties, undoped PZT has a remanent polarisation of $50\text{-}75 \mu\text{C/cm}^2$ [28]. By increasing the density, the dielectric constants and piezoelectric rise from 330 and 60 pC/N to 680 and 240 pC/N respectively [29]. The PZT is used as actuators below 400°C [30].

The studies on PZT doped with [Fe, Bi] were done. Acceptor doping means a free electron is created when a substitution occurs in the lattice such as adding Fe^{3+} to a Pb^{4+} B-site.

The acceptor doping results in lower permittivity and piezoelectric coupling, conversely, donor doping is the substitution where an electron hole is left, such as doping Bi^{3+} onto the Pb^{2+} A-site in PZT. The donor doping leads to higher permittivity and piezoelectric coupling [28]. The environmental issues led to find lead free alternatives and they include BaTiO_3 , $\text{Bi}_{1/2}\text{Na}_{1/2}\text{TiO}_3$ and NKN-based ceramics, like $\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{NbO}_3$ (NKN), and $\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5}\text{TiO}_3$ (NBT), based etc. [31-39].

It is clear from the figure 5 shows that lead free piezoelectric ceramics have inferior piezoelectricity compared to that of PZT. The recent works shows that their performance limit has been increased to a higher level [41] but yet not reached to the level of most desired PZT based systems.

Figure 5: Piezoelectric performance versus curie temperature [40]

Lead Free Piezoelectric Perovskites

Potassium Niobate, KnbO_3 [Kn]: The KN is a perovskite material with $T_C = 425^\circ\text{C}$. Below this temperature, the tetragonal phase is prominent until the temperature falls to 220°C . Below this temperature it changes to an orthorhombic structure and at $T_C = -140^\circ\text{C}$, to rhombohedral phase which is shown in figure 6. All these phase transition temperatures are much above those of BT [35]. Shirane reported these transition temperatures to be 435 , 225 and -110°C [42]. Due to the lower melting point of KN at about 1050°C , it is difficult to obtain well sintered KN samples. KN has phase symmetries and phase transition sequences identical to BT. Matthias and Remieka reported the ferroelectric behaviour of KN in 1951 [43] which exhibits spontaneous polarisation from $0.9 \mu\text{C/cm}^2$ at room temperature to $26 \mu\text{C/cm}^2$ near T_C . The processing of KN is difficult since K_2O is volatile and evaporates at high temperatures [44].

Figure 6: The dielectric constant hysteresis behaviour of KN with respect to temperature (after Megaw, 1967) [35].

Barium Titanate [BaTiO_3 or Bt]: The BT was the first smart material which was chosen as lead free piezoelectric to replace the lead based counterparts. The BT is the ferroelectric perovskite material with classic cubic structure as in figure 7 shows the barium cations in the corner A-site positions and the oxygen anions at the centre of the cell faces creating a face centred cubic structure.

The octahedral interstice with B-site at the centre is occupied with a titanium ($4+$) cation. Due to the high polarizability of barium titanate, it can easily form a permanent dipole below $T_C = 130^\circ\text{C}$, its curie temperature [4]. At room temperature, the tetragonal phase of BT was stable and from the figure 8, it was observed that the cubic edges are elongated, while the other two were decreased in length slightly, thereby maintaining the same ratio to each other [42]. BT can be metastable at room temperature in the hexagonal unit cell.

Figure 7: BaTiO_3 cubic crystal structure above 130°C

As the temperature decreases below freezing, the edges between the two sides of equal length distort their 90° edges to create an orthorhombic unit cell and this transition took place at 5°C [45]. The final phase transformation occurs at -90°C , where the lengthened edge c , shortens to the same length as the other two parameters. At this stage the right angles vanishes in the unit cell as all sides are under shear thereby creating a rhombohedral structure. The exact transition temperatures can vary due to impurities, doping, grain size, and stress conditions of the sample.

The dielectric constant of BT was found to be grain size dependent [46-48]. The room temperature dielectric constant of grain size 10 micron BT ceramics was found to be in the range of 1500–2000, while BT ceramics with grain size 1 micron exhibit an enhanced room temperature dielectric constant between 3500–6000. The dependence of grain size on the room temperature dielectric constant has been explained by Buessem et al., who studied that the internal stresses in finely sized grains of BT must be much greater than in the larger grains of BT, thereby leading to a higher permittivity at room temperature [49]. This shows that small grains are required to sustain a large dielectric constant.

Figure 8: Phase structures of Barium titanate

By doping BT with other perovskite materials, the T_C may decrease or increase depending upon the dopant. If 30% of $SrTiO_3$ added as dopant to BT, then the temperature decreases from 130 °C to below zero. T_C can be altered by the addition of Pb, Ca, Sr, Zr and Sn dopants on the Ba^{2+} A-site [6].

Polycrystalline $BaTiO_3$ exhibits dielectric constants of a few thousand and piezoelectric coefficients close to 200 pC/N [50]. The discovery of the high dielectric constant of BT was one of the fundamental issues in the understanding of ferroelectricity and piezoelectricity in ceramics. BT does not exhibit high piezoelectric constants but it has high relative permittivity. For this reason, BT is the most widely used material in capacitors. Above 107°C, the ferroelectric P-E hysteresis loops become pinched in the middle, creating two smaller hysteresis loops [51]. This antiferroelectric behaviour is observed till 128°C where a straight line is formed in replacement of hysteresis. Hence paraelectric behaviour begins very close to the 130 °C [4]. Berlincourt et al. in the year 1971 reported a BT with room temperature d_{33} value ~ 190 pC/N[52]. The room temperature d_{33} ~ 260 pC/N, was achieved through the synthesis of BT powder by solid state reaction route [53].

Figure 9: The phase diagram of the BaO-TiO₂ system [4].

Sodium Niobate [Nn]: Kakimoto reported a T_C for NN to be around 365°C similar to that of PZT and reported that NN undergoes seven phase transitions as temperature increases[44] showing its sensitivity to temperature. It is known to be antiferroelectric [42] and when subjected to an electric field produces two hysteresis loops, one each in the positive and negative applied field directions. The structure of NN is orthorhombic but antiferroelectric at room temperature till 360°C ($\pm 15^\circ$ C), and undergoes a phase transition to pseudo-tetragonal at 375°C and becomes paraelectric cubic from 640°C.

The material becomes ferroelectric in its monoclinic phase, which occurs at -200°C. The phase transitions are highly sensitive to internal strains, and exact transitions were found after annealing the sample according to Reisman [54]. The large differences between the rhombohedral-orthorhombic phase transitions was reported by

space groups are mentioned and the oxygen tilting is mentioned with subscripts 0, + and – which denotes the direction of tilting in the x, y and z axes [60]. Zhang et al showed that a sintering temperature of 1060°C produced fully saturated hysteresis loops with Pr and Ec being 15 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and 13 kV/cm respectively in a 4 kV/mm field and d_{33} nearly equal to 122 pC/N. NKN is very difficult to sinter and densify. Zhang et al. investigated the variation of hysteresis behaviour as a function of sintering temperature [61] and they showed that a sintering temperature of 1020°C led to a density of 69.4%. When the same composition was sintered at 1080°C, densification reached a higher value of 94.4% which produced fully saturated hysteresis loops. This shows the importance of sintering temperature in the processing of NKN ceramics.

Many researchers used an orthorhombic phase of NKN for the refining the cell parameters at room temperature from X-ray diffraction (XRD) [62] and monoclinic phase with cell parameters $a = 4.0001 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.9473 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 3.9997 \text{ \AA}$ and angle $\beta = 90^\circ 30'$ [63]. Piezoelectric properties for undoped NKN of $d_{33} = 80 \text{ pC/N}$ [29] and a higher value of 105 pC/N is reported [64, 65]. Ichiki et al. found ferroelectric hysteresis in NKN to have Pr = 8.9 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ and Ec = 9.0 kV/cm [66] but higher remnant polarisations have been studied [67-70].

Hot-pressed NKN possesses high remnant polarization (33 $\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$) and $d_{33} = 160 \text{ pC/N}$ [71]. Some new sintering aids like $\text{K}_4\text{CuNb}_8\text{O}_{23}$ [72, 73] and $\text{K}_{5.4}\text{CuTa}_{10}\text{O}_{29}$ [74] was utilized to improve the sintering of NKN. The microstructures formed were denser than those of NKN sintered without them. [75-78].

Many studies have been carried out on many NKN-based composites, such as NKN–LiTaO₃ [79], NKN–LiNbO₃ [80], NKN–LiSbO₃ [81], NKN–SrTiO₃ [82-84] NKN–BaTiO₃ [36], NKN–AgNbO₃. (1-x)KNN-xLiSbO₃/NKN-LS is a solid solution of NKN and LiSbO₃ (LS) systems and it was investigated that the enhanced properties in NKN-LS ceramics is due to a polymorphic phase transition [85, 87]. Even though NKN-LS ceramics has excellent piezoelectric properties but it is not comparable to PZT ceramics. Lei et al. reported that the substitution of Ag⁺ ion in NKN ceramics resulted in an improvement in d_{33} value ~186 pC/N and the relative density equal to 94% of the theoretical density [84]. Xu et al also reported that Ag⁺ ion enters the NKN lattice to form a new system with improved electrical properties compared to pure NKN ceramics. It was also reported that the tantalum doping in NKN helps to improve the piezoelectric properties.

The reported values of d_{33} of $\{[\text{Li}_x(\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{K}_{0.5})_{1-x}]\text{NbO}_3\}$ ($x = 0.04-0.20$) was 200–235 pC/N [88], $(\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})_{0.96-x}\text{Li}_x\text{Sr}_{0.02}\text{Nb}_{0.098}\text{Sb}_{0.02}\text{O}_3$ was 142 pC/N [89] and CaTiO₃ modified $[(\text{K}_{0.5}\text{Na}_{0.5})_{0.96}\text{Li}_{0.04}](\text{Nb}_{0.91}\text{Sb}_{0.05}\text{Ta}_{0.04})\text{O}_3$ was 263 pC/N [90] respectively. (KNN)-based textured ceramics with high $d_{33} = 416 \text{ pC/N}$ was synthesized by Saito et al. And found that the high piezoelectric properties was due to polymorphic phase transition between orthorhombic and tetragonal phases [91]. The studies on the structural and electrical properties of NBT and its dopants have reported values of d_{33} of $(\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5})_{1-x}\text{Ba}_x\text{TiO}_3$ was 180 pC/N, NBT–BT_{0.11} to be 13 pC/N [92], (KNN–LT–BNT–BT) composite to be 155 pC/N [93]. $(\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5})\text{TiO}_3$ doped with 5 mol% BaTiO₃ (NBT–BT_{0.05}) ~ 77 pC/N [94] respectively. These reported values of d_{33} are far less than the corresponding lead based ceramics. Liu et al. reported a lead free [BZT–BCT] ferroelectric system to replace PZT based systems with high $d_{33} \sim 620 \text{ pC/N}$ [95]. Satoshi et al synthesized BT-NKN composites at different sintering temperatures and piezoelectric parameter was calculated to be 103 pC/N for sintering temperature 1020 °C and 78 pC/N for 1045 °C [96]. The impedance spectroscopy and dielectric studies of nanocrystalline iron doped barium strontium titanate ceramics was studied [97]. The impedance data indicates that the relaxations in the samples are due to the presence of polarizing species which contribute to grain boundary capacitance and conductance. The σ_{ac} conductivity plots confirm the Jonscher's power law and the temperature dependence of dc conductivity proves the hopping mechanism in the sample.

The piezoelectric, impedance, and conductivity studies of $(\text{Na}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_{0.5})_{1-x}\text{Ba}_x\text{TiO}_3$ was studied. The longitudinal piezoelectric charge coefficients of the (1 – x) BNT_{1-x} BT samples poled under a dc electric field of about 2.5kV/mm at 80 °C/15 min lie in the range of 17–124 pC/N. The complex impedance analysis in the frequency range 100Hz-1MHz indicates the presence of grain-boundary effect and bulk contribution and also confirms the presence of the non-Debye type of multiple relaxations in the materials [98]. The study of BaTiO₃ admixtures on the properties of the NKN ferroelectric ceramics reveals that the growth of the BT content increases the conductivity of the material [99]. The frequency and temperature dependent dielectric and conductivity behavior of KNbO₃ ceramics was investigated and found that the mechanism of the low-frequency dielectric relaxation is due to relaxations in oxygen vacancy related dipoles and conductivity due to the oxygen vacancy hopping conduction [100]. The dielectric constant increases, with temperature up to 190°C and it then decreases with increase of temperature. The structural phase transition from tetragonal to orthorhombic phase occurs at about 190°C. The electrical conductivity increases with temperature and material shows semiconductor like behaviour

with increasing temperature [101]. Among these, BT with lower and NKN with higher curie temperature marks them as promising candidates for high temperatures applications.

Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA): The PVA is a creamy or whitish, tasteless, odourless, nontoxic, biocompatible, thermostable linear synthetic polymer. It has large dielectric strength and excellent charge storage ability. Its mechanical, optical and electrical properties can readily be tailored by doping with nano fillers [123]. The monomeric structure of PVA is shown in Figure 12. It was first synthesized by Hermann and Haehnel in 1924 by saponifying poly (vinyl ester) with sodium hydroxide solution.

Figure 12: Structure of polyvinyl alcohol

The physicochemical and mechanical properties of PVA are governed by the number of hydroxyl groups present in the PVA polymer. The basic raw material for the polymerization of PVA is vinyl acetate (as monomer) and the controlled partial alkaline hydrolysis of vinyl acetate is performed where the ester group of vinyl acetate is replaced by the hydroxyl group in the presence of aqueous sodium hydroxide. The resulting precipitate of this reaction is called PVA.

Developments in Ferroelectric Ceramic-Polymer Composites: Newnham et al introduced piezoelectric composites which combined passive polymer matrices with piezoelectric ceramic particles, utilizing the specific advantages of each material to overcome the low flexibility of ceramics and the low piezoelectricity of polymers [10, 102–104].

Several researchers have tried to prepare polymer based 0-3 composites, using different ferroelectric ceramics as fillers and polymers as matrix. 0–3 ceramic-polymer perovskite type ferroelectric ceramics, such as BT, PZT, PMN–PT and NKN, etc have been well studied [105-111]. Ceramic–polymer composites, especially of type 0–3, are a potential material group suitable for producing demanding and functional packages that combine the electrical properties of ceramics and the mechanical flexibility, chemical stability, and processing possibilities of polymers. It is well known that the connectivity between the phases in the composite materials is very important in achieving the desired properties [112, 10]. The dielectric studies of PZT/PVA investigated by Uma et al showed that dielectric permittivity increases with volume fraction and this increase in permittivity is attributed to the internal polarization in the sample [113].

The piezoelectric ceramic PZT and PVDF composite resulted in 50% increase in d_{33} values [114]. Composites of PT (Ca) and P (VDF-TrFE) were studied and it was found that a d_{33} value of 55 pC/N could be achieved [115]. Their conclusion was that though the d_{33} increased, the g_{33} was naturally lowered. PZT/PVDF composite was synthesized which showed a better dispersion of PZT in PVDF matrix. P-E loops indicate the remnant polarization to be about $0.24\mu\text{C}/\text{cm}^2$ for 50% PZT- PVDF film. The piezoelectric strain coefficient (d_{33}) have been analysed for the PZT/PVDF composites and it was found that the values of d_{33} increases with volume fraction. But in the case of polymers like PVDF-TrFE and PVC with PZT, the d_{33} are nonlinear. This is due to the fact that ceramic and polymer phases are polarized in opposite direction [116]. Due to environmental issues of toxic lead, researchers focussed on lead free ceramic materials. For the better performance of 0-3 composites, polymer matrix plays an important role. Many polymers have been used based on their processibility, flexibility, melting temperature, glass transition temperature and dielectric strength. Polymer matrices most commonly used are poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), polyaniline (PANI), polyurethane (PU), etc. Presently, high dielectric constant PVDF and high mechanical strength epoxies are focussed [117-120]. A comparative study of complex dielectric properties of BT/PAni/resin composites was investigated by Pant et al. [105]. This study showed that

the composites of BaTiO₃ /maleic resin revealed normal composite behaviour and a dielectric constant which followed asymmetric Bruggeman model. In contrast, the composites of BaTiO₃ /PAni showed a drastic reduction in the dielectric constant of BaTiO₃ according to Hajeesaeh et al., [106]. The dielectric properties of BT-PVDF 0-3 composites which showed that at a low volume fraction of BT ceramics, dielectric constant of the composite at room temperature and 1 kHz frequency were found to be 11.5. Li, Ta, Sb modified NKN/PVDF 0-3 composites was synthesized and their piezoelectric and dielectric properties were studied by Seol et al. [117]. Alexandre et al investigated the piezoelectric properties of NN/PVDF and found d₃₃ equal to 6.5 pC/N for NN nanowires and 2.6 pC/N for nano particles [121]. These composites exhibited better piezoelectric and dielectric properties than the PZT/polymer based composites.

Conclusions

From all these observations, conclusions can be drawn that lot of efforts are being done to enhance the structural, piezoelectric property, dielectric permittivity, etc. of ceramic-polymer composites. Zhang et al studied dielectric properties of BT (Fe)/PVDF and found that dielectric permittivity increases with filler volume upto 33%, and then decreases as the weight exceeds 33 vol% [122]. The dielectric constant values of BT-PC composites was studied and it increased with the volume percentage of BT. The dielectric permittivity of the composites at 30 and 70 vol% were 190 and 436, respectively and d₃₃ values found to increase from 10 to 16 pC/N when the volume of BT increased from 50 to 70 vol%.

Most of the research is focussed on ferroelectric polymers and lead based and lead free piezoelectric ceramics. Less attempts are observed on non-ferroelectric polymer matrices that to on PVA.

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